

Final Evaluation of the Opening the Future Revenue Model

Some Thoughts and Conclusions at
the End of the Copim Open Book
Futures Project

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Introduction

Many strands of phase 2 of the Copim project (Copim Open Book Futures 2023–2026) have involved hands-on research, where hypotheses are explored and tested, and results generated by actually doing the work. Among these is Opening the Future (Copim Work Package 3, also known as OtF) and, in the day-to-day busyness of running an operational funding programme, it has sometimes been easy to forget that our jobs also entail, at their core, undertaking experimental research.

We were investigating whether collective funding could be implemented for small-medium sized, mission-driven presses and if a way could be found to do this that was sustainable and realistic for these often financially precarious publishers. It is important to remember that in 2019, when the initial COPIM project began, it was by no means certain that this could be done. While by this point there were a handful of individual book publishers who had been partially sustaining themselves via library memberships for some time (Open Book Publishers since 2014, Lever Press since 2016, punctum books since 2018, and a journal analogue in the Open Library of Humanities since 2015), and one major

collective funding scheme for books that publishers could access on a per-title basis (Knowledge Unlatched since 2012), the field was still young, and the particular model being trialled by Opening the Future took a different approach to all of the previous ones. Its innovation was to take subscriptions to a closed backlist and use them to fund new, open access frontlist books. So rather than taking the form of ‘pure’ frontlist support, OtF monetises the press’ existing closed backlist by packaging it up and turning library subscriptions to these packages into permanent access after three years. In this way it is essentially a delayed purchase, allowing libraries to access collections budgets to support the frontlist non-BPC OA publishing endeavours of OtF-participating presses. Devised by Professor Martin Eve, then at Birkbeck College, UoL, he announced it in a blog post in 2020: *Backlist to the Future: a new business model for university presses and open-access books*¹.

Backlist to the Future

The model was devised to leverage backlist books that for all intents and purposes cannot be flipped themselves. Flipping a closed backlist to open is tricky due to the complications, uncertainty, and prohibitive costs associated with gaining retrospective permissions, and logistical difficulties like digitisation and conversion to accessible formats. Instead, OtF’s ‘USP’ was to use this closed backlist as a benefit or lever to allow presses to systematically and incrementally move away from paywalled publishing in a low risk manner.

By early 2023, when the first phase of the project ended (COPIM 2019-2023) and the Copim ‘Open Book Futures’ (Copim OBF 2023-2026) project began, many uncertainties remained around OtF’s suitability and sustainability and the model was still in the early days of implementation.

All of which is to say that this was truly experimental, and undertaken without the assumption that this could be implemented in a sustainable, financially viable, and long-lasting manner. In many ways, our ‘experiment’ has been a resounding success on a number of fronts. Firstly, we achieved all of our stated project deliverables. There are a number of related deliverables around outreach to libraries and publishers that are [written up as various posts on the Copim blog](#), but the overall aim of Opening the Future via Work Package 3 of Copim Open Book Futures was to transition three additional presses to the programme, joining CEU Press and Liverpool University Press who had been the initial pilot participants since 2021. This we have achieved, launching with Michigan State University Press in June 2025, Boydell & Brewer in October 2025, and Basler Afrika Bibliographien in February 2026. We felt very strongly that these publishers should be able to continue their OtF programmes beyond the project and that other presses interested in the model should have a trusted source of information, so we gave ourselves another major deliverable - to publish an Information Hub with detailed information, cost calculators, templates, and other materials for publishers looking to implement their own version of Opening the Future. This [was completed in mid-2025](#) as part of our broader work on the Copim Compass, the delivery of which was led by WP3 on behalf of the Copim OBF team.

¹ Martin Paul Eve, "Backlist to the Future: a new business model for university presses and open-access books", <https://eve.gd>, October 22, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.59348/f8xr5-pw254>

Successes

Beyond the deliverables, we are proud of several further achievements. So far, our participating publishers have raised c. £700,000 cumulatively - funding approximately 70 new OA titles that would otherwise have been behind a paywall (44 already published and 26 in various stages of production). We have also been able to see these books being used widely - [OAPEN data for 2025 showed that, via that platform alone, OtF-funded titles were cumulatively accessed over 19,500 times from January to October](#). The OtF-funded titles at Liverpool University Press were accessed a total of 4,095 times from January to October 2025. The OtF-funded titles at CEU Press, meanwhile, were accessed 15,433 times in that same period, for a combined total of 19,528 times. Excluding any other platforms they were read on, this means that the OtF-funded books were read on average 64 times per day in 2025. Or, to look at this another way, averaged out across all 39 titles, that's around 500 accesses per title. This is OAPEN usage data only - the books are all available on multiple other platforms including JSTOR and MUSE, so these figures are indicative, meaning that total usage and uptake is likely much greater still. This 2025 usage is indicative of other years.

We have also been fortunate enough to have feedback from some of the participating authors on how meaningful the ability to publish OA has been for them (those testimonials are available on our blog site ²). Their experiences provide valuable qualitative data on the positive impact that this funding can have for many researchers such as independent scholars and those working with marginalised communities.

Behind those headline numbers another success has been in creating and nurturing a network of five very diverse publishers (traditional University Presses in the UK and US, an employee-owned for-profit press based primarily in the UK, and a tiny European society publisher); a global community of over 150 library investor members; and a network of supporting infrastructure partners stretching from the USA to Switzerland to Southern Africa.

But perhaps the top achievement of WP3 is really that we've demonstrated a route to OA collective funding for the types of publishers that are most likely to be left behind in a mass shift to OA for books. No other projects or initiatives have really focused on these types of publishers, and yet there are a great many of them in Europe, America, the UK and beyond: smaller mission-led presses that have a traditionally closed (or partially-closed) access background and history, and smaller for-profits and societies. Other projects and orgs like DeGruyter, JSTOR, or MIT, and indeed our colleagues on the Open Book Collective (OBC), have between them helped to create avenues to financial support for larger university presses, pure non-profit presses, and for born-OA publishers. And of course the very large commercial publishers can move towards OA books themselves without the need for help from a project like ours (for example Taylor & Francis) but the main thing Work Package 3 has demonstrated is that Opening the Future can work for lots of publisher types no matter how into OA they already are. That seems important and quite unique - an approach like this will be needed if the scholarly publishing sector is going to preserve the rich and bibliodiverse publishing cultures we desire.

² [OtF author Profile: Tess C. Rankin](#); [OtF author Profile: Dean Allbritton](#); [OtF author Profile: Daniel Silva](#); [OtF Author Profile: Mario Graña Taborelli](#); [OtF Author Profile: Peter Watson](#); [OtF author interview Tomasz Kamusella](#)

Challenges

It is important to make space for these successes here as we consider the outcomes of the project. However, it is equally (if not more) important to note that some original hypotheses on which the model was designed have turned out to be flawed, that some results of our experimentation have been negative, and that we have encountered - and continue to encounter - many difficulties in this work. In this report, we want to give space to these aspects for two main reasons: to fully record the outcomes of Opening the Future as a Work Package in a research project, and to help others looking to implement similar projects in the future to anticipate and overcome potential obstacles.

Many of these difficulties have either arisen from, or had a light shone on them by, an additional goal we set ourselves outside of our defined deliverables: we wanted to ensure that the model has as much longevity as possible, and to make it as easy as possible for new publishers to adopt this without our direct help. This crystallised into the concept of finding a third-party 'home' for the model which could facilitate its ongoing implementation.

Why a 'Home' Became Necessary for Opening the Future

This 'home' became more important as we went through the process of trying to onboard the three new publishers - WP3's main deliverable. We began our efforts to bring on more presses in early 2024 and, in addition to the three publishers that eventually launched an OtF programme, we spoke (to varying extents) with around twelve others. While these other twelve fell by the wayside for a variety of reasons, there was a strong common theme between many of them: our inability to guarantee external support of some kind after April 2026 (i.e. after the Open Book Futures project ended). It is important to note here though that this lack of external support was not an oversight on the part of WP3/Opening the Future in the initial design, it was always supposed to be the case.

Initial Hypotheses and Some Subsequent Tough Lessons Learned

Structurally and legally, there is no Opening the Future. Unlike the two Copim infrastructures, the Open Book Collective and Thoth Open Metadata, which are both registered charities, OtF is not a business. While it raises funds, we have no bank account; instead the programme facilitates direct financial relationships between libraries and publishers. While WP3 advises on, and facilitates, agreements between publishers, libraries, and third party providers, we are not ourselves participants in these agreements. This was entirely by design, and was a legacy of Copim Phase 1: under that project [an OtF implementation guide](#) and a GitHub of our code for the back office system was made freely available in 2023. One of the initial hypotheses in Copim Phase 1 was that publishers might be able to implement OtF more or less entirely in-house, perhaps analogously to how a publisher traditionally manages their sales and marketing. So as part of Copim Phase 2 we pledged to expand on this and create the [Copim Compass](#) - making the implementation guide more interactive and detailed. Later in this report we return to the lessons learned on how realistic it was to hope that presses would be able to go it alone using the Compass guide (see § *What Were the Bare Bones? Notes For Future Initiatives*).

It was believed during the design stage of Copim Phase 1 that open access broadly, and Diamond OA in particular, were general major directions of travel for academic book publishing. This certainly has turned out to be correct in the UK, as evidenced by the UKRI monograph mandate of 2024 which also [made explicit provision for supporting collective funding schemes](#) and the Wellcome Trust who from 2025 have allowed their funds to libraries to be used on collective funding schemes. In the UK there is the as yet un-dated REF OA requirement for books from January 2029 and in Europe more monograph mandates than ever before, including from the European Commission.³ Searching by year for publications on OAPEN also suggests growth over time in the number of book titles published OA.

This prediction of the general direction of travel for OA books led to two hypotheses for WP3 under Copim Phases 1 and 2: that this would be a major priority for publishers, and that library budgets would radically reform to entrench support of Diamond OA. While funders have begun to explicitly carve out a space for collective funding, as noted above, the [decision by the four UK funding bodies not to mandate OA books in the current REF cycle](#) has put a pause on many discussions in libraries around prioritising sustainable OA book funding. And while some libraries have added Diamond OA support into their institutional policies (e.g. [Sheffield](#) in the UK, KU Leuven in Belgium), we have found that both of our assumptions have not entirely been borne out. There has been some shift in a handful of library budgets around enshrining budgets for use in collective funding programmes, and some very encouraging developments around this in the UK funder policies, but the rate and degree of change have been less than anticipated.

We have wondered if this was partly due to a perception bias on our part: a degree of false consensus. In our jobs, we deal with, and advocate to, institutional libraries daily. One of the WP3 team members has a library background stretching back to 1996 (having worked at the University of Leeds library, the University of York library and at White Rose University Press before joining the COPIM Project) - we are therefore very familiar with libraries, but what we may not have fully appreciated is that libraries are large, complex, and segmented organisations driven by a set of policies and stakeholders which are sometimes in tension with one another. The acquisitions, open research, and scholarly communications librarians with whom we have the most contact are but three parts of this machine.

Frontlist vs Backlist Library Investment

Our experience of these librarians has been something of a confirmation bias - they themselves are passionate advocates and, in our experience, have endless talents for finding and investing small pots of money to support OA initiatives they feel strongly about. It is to them that we owe much of the financial successes that OtF has had, including the backlist acquisition component of the model - more on this in a moment. But budgetary changes of the volume and nature that Opening the Future anticipated occur at a higher level within the library, and are also in part influenced by decision-makers who sit above the library entirely, and with whom different arguments must be made, as they themselves have a broader view of priorities and risks that face the institution. Additionally, changes of this nature occur on longer timescales than the length of our project. The nature of the models that have followed our own launch is

³ See [Annex A: Overview of existing OA book policies of a subset of cOAlition S organisations](#)

instructive. As noted above, earlier collective funding models for books were pure frontlist support, while Opening the Future is not. MIT Direct to Open, which launched the same year as Opening the Future, also opted not to go for pure frontlist support - it provides access to some of its closed access books for the duration of the library subscription. Subsequent models have also largely opted to avoid pure frontlist support, for example:

- [JSTOR Path to Open](#) (2023),
- [UMP Fund to Mission](#) (2021),
- [Taylor and Francis Pledge to Open](#) (2023)
- [Bloomsbury Open Collections](#) (2023)

These all provide library members access to otherwise paywalled material, while [De Gruyter's UPLOpen](#) (2024) has built their collective funding into their closed access UPL distribution network by retaining a small share of these library subscription fees, an approach similar to that of [Lived Places](#), a small, independent scholarly press who set up their own collective funding scheme in 2024. One notable exception to all of these is of course the Open Book Collective (2024), a Copim infrastructure, which provides pure frontlist support, with the added benefit not of closed content access, but offering libraries a share in the governance of the charity, reframing them from customer to partner.

The importance of the backlist element of the Opening the Future model was discussed with our Library Advisory Board in 2025, as we were considering future variations on the model at the time, and it was made clear to us by the board members that the backlist package was a vital aspect of the model and a major reason to participate from their perspective. Many libraries we have spoken to over the course of the project have echoed this sentiment, and have also added that even when the frontlist support is their main reason for participating, having the 'lever' of the backlist package can be very valuable when they are seeking to get the necessary buy-in from budget holders or other parties in the library. This feedback from our members was reinforced by an influential report in August 2025 from Ithaka S+R where OtF was mentioned as an example of "models [that] show promise for libraries in that they represent an intersection between meeting content demand, pivoting the institution to greater support of open content, and promoting responsible financial models." One librarian quoted in the report stated that the value of OtF was that "the library views it more as a subscription model plus supporting open access as opposed to providing open access support alone." ⁴

This point about the more equivocal benefits of the backlist, that of the lever, further support the point that library policy, budget, and perspectives outside of the open research teams are still changing, and that therefore more conventional elements of collective funding models, in particular bundling OA frontlist support with closed content access, has a part to play in these changes as they play out over a longer time period than we initially hoped. It remains to be seen whether these direct benefits will always remain necessary for broader buy-in, or if, as the landscape matures and entrenches, we will see a more widespread take-up of the more purely altruistic frontlist support models that innovated collective funding for books. Additionally, we can hope that our own wide advocacy around the financial and social benefits of collective funding, and our own tangible success, can provide evidence for those in the libraries who are trying to pull those levers more lastingly.

⁴ Bergstrom, Tracy, and Makala Skinner. "The Current State of Academic E-Book Business Models: Access Strategies and Budgeting Realities." Ithaka S+R. Ithaka S+R. 13 August 2025. Web. 23 April 2026. <https://doi.org/10.18665/sr.323373>

Some Initial Conclusions

There have also been some encouraging signs for the future in the last couple of years, largely in the form of [several UK HEI walkaways from the journal Big Deals](#). While it is vital to contextualise these walkaways within the current financial crisis impacting universities and their libraries, it can still be hoped that a period of time outside of these deals, although brought about by financial stress as well as by strategic change, will evidence the ability of libraries to function without them. Another encouraging development has been the growth of evaluation criteria that indicate the enshrinement of collective funding within decision-making processes in many libraries. Finally, the support that has poured in worldwide for collective funding initiatives such as our own (cumulatively, since 2021, Opening the Future has raised c. £700,000 and since 2024 the Open Book Collective has raised c. £1,400,000) has shown resoundingly that despite straitened financial circumstances, libraries do in fact want to fund these types of collective funding schemes.

Nevertheless, despite many reasons for longer-term optimism, the funding and library budget landscape is not where we expected/hoped it would be back in 2021 when this project was being planned. Similarly, our contact with numerous publishers since 2023 suggests that we overestimated their capacity to run in-house, or even participate in, a collective funding scheme like ours. One publisher we spoke to said that they had enough on their plate ‘just trying to keep the lights on’ and this phrase summarises the feedback of most that we spoke to: there were too many other demands on their human and financial resources to take on an OA programme that was not, as yet, widely mandated (even if they personally would have liked to pursue it for ethical reasons). Others pointed out that even if they theoretically had time to dedicate to running a collective funding programme internally, they lacked the experience and skills in library outreach that are necessary to do this effectively. With every publisher we talked to, it became increasingly clear that we had overestimated the capacity of the average small, scholarly press (both independent and institutional) to absorb a project of this kind into their day to day operations. This conclusion was supported by the fact that, although all of the documentation for running an Opening the Future-type model [had been published in mid-2022](#), with the goal of supporting publishers to set up their own OtF programme, we were not aware of any publishers having done so in the intervening few years.

These conclusions are also supported by the three publishers we did onboard during this phase who all, in different ways, perpetuated the original spirit of ‘pilot experimentation’ from Copim phase 1. Michigan State University Press (MSUP), during our onboarding discussions, expressed a wish to give this a go and see what happened, stating that as it was (by design) low-risk for publishers, it was worth giving it a go. This partnership possibly also benefited from close knowledge by the team at MSUP of UMP’s Fund to Mission, a similar initiative to Opening the Future that also launched in 2021, due to an overlap of staff experiences at MSUP. Boydell and Brewer, meanwhile, also expressed a desire to try new things and to develop better links with and understanding of libraries. This attitude is further evidenced by their contemporary development of the [Horizons project](#) supporting early career researchers to publish OA monographs. Finally, Basler Afrika Bibliographien are, to the best of our knowledge, the first society publisher to participate in a collective funding model for books like ours and also expressed a desire to experiment with new ways to support their authors and disseminate their publications as openly as

possible, in keeping with their charitable mission. This collective attitude of experimentation may suggest that, from the publisher's perspective at least, these models are still viewed as novelty whose long-term viability and value is still untested.

It was as these conversations were playing out during 2024 and early 2025, and as we began to appreciate that from both a library and a publisher perspective, the field was not as matured as we had hoped by this point, that this data crystallised into the requirement that we find a 'home' for Opening the Future, so that there would be a point of contact and support post-project, providing both the benefits and the appearance of continuity and sustainability. We also realised that this would help to encourage new publishers to adopt it after the project ended.

What Overarching Infrastructure is Necessary to Support a Revenue Model Like Ours?

Firstly, a minor segue - in mid-2024 there were brief discussions between the two WP3 team members on whether OtF itself could (and should) become a full infrastructure to support the work past the point of the project ending. We found ourselves in mild disagreement about this point - on the one hand, we calculated that a share of the collected revenues may be able to support 0.5 FTE of OtF staff, which would be able to do the necessary administrative work, and some outreach. This level of continuity may also have given participating publishers peace of mind, and helped to onboard new publishers. But on the other hand, this would be a highly precarious infrastructure requiring some personal commitment and something of a leap of faith - therefore, it may be better to embed OtF in an existing third party infrastructure that has greater sustainability, resilience, and wider name recognition.

These conversations came to a natural end when we realised that they were somewhat academic in nature - in fact, it was virtually impossible to retrofit Opening the Future into a full infrastructure in its own right. We canvassed librarians who said they would be willing for a portion of library revenues to be retained to support some FTE to run Opening the Future, in much the same way as, for example, the Open Book Collective. Our publishers were also in principle not opposed to this, but noted that the prices of our backlist packages, which had been formulated to be as low as possible, were not viable minus the necessary estimated 10-20% cut to support FTE. It was functionally difficult to raise the prices by this amount due to the policies of the third party billing agents we rely on for UK and US libraries, the bulk of our library revenue, which restrict annual price rises to an inflationary 5% maximum. We could have presented a good business case for raising the prices by being transparent about the reason and we believe the library members and presses would have been supportive of it because it would help to ensure the longevity of the programme - but, again, it would have required some personal commitment from one or both of us that neither was in a position to make. We would urge anyone setting up a collective funding scheme to bear in mind though that when setting their initial prices, once they've been agreed with third parties, it will be almost impossible to meaningfully increase them. This has had an impact on us, as outlined here, but we have also heard frustration from some other low-priced initiatives who have found that rising costs have increasingly outpaced this cap.

Our publishers were in multi-year agreements with these invoicing partners - not easy to change mid-cycle. While it may have been possible to quickly register as a CIC or full charity, draw together some governance and open a bank account, and make the case to the libraries for raising the prices we decided against it. We also concluded that, by the time we were having these debates (in late 2024 and early 2025) there was not enough time left of the Open Book Futures project to register as a full charity and instigate robust and well-considered governance alongside our other full time duties, thus making it even more likely that any infrastructure we created would ultimately fail.

Despite these initial (and ultimately, rejected) explorations of creating our own infrastructure, it remained clear that a light touch infrastructure of *some* kind was necessary to help small, mission-driven publishers to function in the increasingly competitive collective funding market, often against large group initiatives that have dedicated outreach and/or sales teams, and to help engage new participating publishers.

A Third Party ‘Home’ for Opening the Future: Pros and Cons

This certainty led us to seek a home for Opening the Future within existing infrastructure which could provide:

- some outreach to libraries and support for billing,
- an interface for current and future publishers,
- an interface for libraries who had questions about the model,
- and a collective voice and identity of some kind.

We had discussions with a couple of possible options throughout 2025, during which time an unexpected ‘chicken and egg’ situation soon arose.

We were, as outlined above, struggling to get new publishers because we did not have a long-term ‘home’ for the model. Meanwhile, we were struggling to engage potential homes because, until June 2025, we only had two publishers, both of whom had always been open to the idea of taking the model in-house at the end of the Open Book Futures project if necessary. This meant we struggled to look like a viable ‘product’ to these infrastructures. On reflection, we should have approached this situation differently. We approached it reactively and ad hoc, when instead we probably should have taken more concrete and proactive steps. One such step could have been collating a list of publishers who might in principle agree to launch Opening the Future if we had a long-term home, and bringing this list to the potential third party homes to demonstrate future potential. We also vacillated in our outreach efforts from publisher to infrastructure and then from infrastructure back to publisher, when it may have been more effective to do both at the same time. However, we are only a team of two with very little business experience between us. We also appreciate that we probably should have budgeted in our initial bid document for consultants in this field who could have helped us to develop a more informed sustainability plan in much the same way as, for example, [the Open Book Collective did with Research Consulting](#). However, as with retrospectively creating an infrastructure, this too was impossible as we simply could not retrospectively add this to our allotted funding, nor could we re-allocate any from

elsewhere in our project budget as this was already relatively modest and already allocated to other activities.

A Roundabout Route to Finding a Home - Setbacks & Changes of Plans

We initially came to a workable solution and a viable new home for our model by late 2025 through an agreement with Lyrisis, the non-profit library consortium based in the USA. Unfortunately, this victory was somewhat short-lived and reflects one of the downsides of relying on a third party for our future plans - they themselves are organisations with capacity and strategies that can change rapidly. Strategic realignments in January 2026 at Lyrisis made it non-viable as a home in the way that we had planned (though, it should be emphasised, this was no one's fault). This too may suggest that setting up as an infrastructure from the start would have been the best option as, at least in that case, we would have been less directly impacted by the strategic changes of parties not directly concerned with Opening the Future.

At the same time another obstacle arose which was directly related to the 'finding a home' piece of work. OtF works because it is underpinned by a set of agreed workflows, and relationships with suppliers and partners⁵ but in early 2026 one of those partners, Jisc (a UK library org that facilitates agreements between libraries and publishers) made some sector-wide decisions as a response to financial pressure on libraries, including introducing a new service fee for all vendors whose agreements are available through their License Subscription Manager (LSM).

As part of this change they decided not to renew our agreement or to take our new OtF publishers on board the LSM, which was a potential blow as listing on there has been instrumental to our success in the UK, one of our main 'markets'. It's the first place UK libraries look when they are investigating programmes in which to invest. One factor in Jisc's decision was that rather than providing a single point of contact between Jisc and publishers (in the way an infrastructure such as the Open Book Collective does), an Opening the Future programme merely facilitates direct relationships between each publisher and Jisc. In other words, Opening the Future is not an infrastructure, it's a mechanism and a set of agreements. This meant that when Jisc were assessing the financial viability of their support for each OA initiative on the LSM, each OtF press had to be assessed individually rather than collectively (unlike, say, the Open Book Collective presses), which meant that they all fell below a newly-introduced threshold of financial viability for Jisc. Cumulatively the presses would have been above this threshold - which leads us to face another hard truth: if the WP3 team had been able to get more presses on board at an earlier stage in the project then the value proposition would have been more attractive to libraries with a broader selection of backlists, and the possibility of a bundled selections or even everything in one big package. A larger investment in a bigger package of backlist books may sound counterintuitive during periods of financial difficulty but the OtF packages are still very good value-for-money and bundling them may have created a more substantial and interdisciplinary addition to collections - perhaps an

⁵ See the [OtF Guiding Principles](#), a set of principles and values agreed by all current partners (note that this link downloads as a PDF).

easier investment for libraries to justify, and a lower administrative overhead for them to engage with and renew.

Ultimately that's just speculation but it's another chicken and egg scenario worth noting. And it is another piece of evidence in favour of the importance of being able to act collectively and at scale - in a way that a more formalised infrastructure would have allowed. The Licensing Team staff we have regular contact with at Jisc have worked tirelessly to find a workable solution in light of Jisc's new policy; we have come up with a potential workaround solution via a joint Jisc agreement with Lyris, with all our publishers being bundled from an administrative standpoint. However, as of 30 April 2026, the details are still being negotiated and it's not a given that an agreement will proceed at all. Our publishers may yet not be able to interface with UK libraries via Jisc, a potentially highly damaging development for the model and another factor in our assessment of 'what is a home' for OtF.

Where We're at Now, in Late April 2026

Following renewed discussions with Lyris since January they have agreed to provide a level of support to the programme's future, in combination with another service provider, the Fulcrum platform (a department of University of Michigan Publishing Services). The latter became involved in Opening the Future with the launch of Boydell & Brewer's participation (as their backlist provider) and have subsequently expressed an interest in being more involved. Under the new joint agreement, Fulcrum will provide ongoing support and hosting of our web pages, a major resource for interested libraries to find out information about our publishers' offerings and to sign up. They will also be the point of contact for onboarding new prospective publishers. Lyris will provide the invoicing service for libraries and will also fulfil some library-facing advocacy and knowledge-sharing about the model.

Therefore, as of 2026, we have fulfilled many of our initial aims around finding a new home:

- we have a continued web presence that interested libraries can easily find,
- our current publishers will remain listed on Lyris and one day potentially on Jisc too,
- we are establishing a community of practice to support current participating publishers and inform interested libraries (more on that below),
- we have a nascent workflow for onboarding new publishers to the programme,
- and we also have these processes fully documented on the Copim Compass.

This home has turned out to be somewhat piecemeal, and unfortunately due to external partners changing direction, this new workflow will come into effect only as the two OtF staff are leaving, meaning that troubleshooting will have to be done without our input or support. However, we are also confident that Lyris, Fulcrum, and our participating publishers have the documentation and workflows in place and cumulatively will be able to find solutions to whatever issues do arise.

Community of Practice & The Importance of Networks & Relationships

We are grateful to Lyrasis and Jisc for their efforts to make OtF work with/despite/around their own institutional realignments, and to Fulcrum for their support and interest in the model, and we are confident that as library-based/library-focused non-profit infrastructures, they are good stewards of the aims and members of Opening the Future. But what must also be noted here is that a large amount of effort and ingenuity had to go into this on the part of our colleagues at these third parties, and that this desire to make it work despite obstacles and to continue our professional relationship was in no small part due to the relationships of mutual trust that had been built since our work with them began in 2021 at the start of the pilot phase of Opening the Future. Without this personal element and the mutual confidence we had in one another, solutions may not have been found in either case.

The setbacks we encountered in finalising a future home, which occurred over late 2025 (and remain, to some extent, ongoing in early 2026), emphasised to us that a collective voice and communal identity would be useful to all the participating publishers when similar issues arise in the future. It also occurred to us that having a forum to share their experiences, the problems they encountered and solutions they found, and perhaps also, where appropriate to undertake joint outreach (e.g. where there is subject overlap between different publishers' packages) would be extremely useful. While Fulcrum will provide the primary home for future participating publishers, as they do now for Boydell & Brewer, we also realised there would be great value in having a space that encompassed all the publishers, including those not on Fulcrum. With this in mind, and with the agreement of all the publishers, we are therefore establishing a new quarterly Community of Practice (CoP), hosted by Lyrasis but voluntarily run by the publishers themselves on rotation. The aim of this CoP is to provide:

- A forum for current OtF publishers, and other presses that are interested in the model, to share knowledge, ask advice, make connections, and agree joint promotional activity etc.
- A forum for current library members, and other libraries that are interested in the model, to make connections, find out more about it or feed back on how it's working for them, what advocacy and budget arguments they use, where the model fits or doesn't fit investment evaluation criteria etc.
- A forum for the current backlist-hosting platforms, and other interested infrastructure providers to share knowledge, ask advice, make connections, and agree joint promotional activity etc.
- A forum for anyone else interested in learning about, or participating in, the OtF OA revenue model and in making scholarly communication freely available to all for public benefit: funders, authors, scholarly communications experts, etc.

Members of our Library Advisory Board, which will cease functioning in April 2026, have also agreed to participate in this shared community space. We also expect that, if it continues to meet over the longer-term, it may seed some as yet unexpected offshoots and developments of Opening the Future.

While our intangible nature has, as outlined above, caused some issues, there is also a great benefit to it - the model remains highly adoptable, adaptable, and malleable. We look forward to seeing over the coming years what directions different parties will take it in.

What Were the Bare Bones? Notes for Future Initiatives

On that point, we also want to briefly cover what steps are necessary for new publishers to engage with Opening the Future. While the logistics are well-covered on our toolkit hosted on the Copim Compass, in particular [our section on workflows and partnerships](#), this lacks some nuance and detail - and for our final deliverable we agreed to reflect back on how best to articulate and how to streamline the whole process.

The Human Element

We were surprised by the degree to which a human element played a factor in the onboarding of the three further publishers who joined during the Open Book Futures project. One of these came about via a chance in-person meeting at a European conference, another via connection from an experienced university publisher in the USA, and the third via a connection with Fulcrum who themselves we first met at another UK conference (after which we pitched OtF to them). A fourth discussion which advanced quite far, but did not ultimately lead to a partnership due to external factors at that press, came about through our close working relationship with our original pilot CEU Press. A fifth that also advanced relatively far also began as a chance discussion at a publishing conference. The degree of correlation between managing to form a partnership and having met in person rather than just remotely was striking to us, and we would recommend that those seeking to implement a model like this attend industry conferences and try to arrange in-person meetings with libraries, platform providers and publishers where possible. This may also speak to the high degree of trust that implementing new publishing programmes requires - face-to-face meetings perhaps have a role to play in building this trust and personal connection.

The other element that is not perfectly captured on our online toolkit is the degree of adaptability of the model. While [our Copim Compass page](#) has a diagram involving Jisc, Lyris and Project MUSE, these are a reflection of our processes at the time of the diagram's creation, rather than concrete rules - although all three infrastructures remain key partners in the current implementation of the model. If we were to recreate the diagram today we'd include Fulcrum and the African Books Collective too. In reality, to make this work, a publisher needs:

1. an infrastructure to manage access to the backlist packages, which can be in-house as in the case of Liverpool University Press, or a third party such as Fulcrum or Project MUSE who can undertake this work for a fee;
2. ideally access to local billing agents in the region you anticipate engagement;
3. And they need to sign agreements or MOUs around these terms between themselves and the third party provider, and both then need to sign contracts with relevant billing agents such as Lyris and Jisc. These agreements are directly between these parties.

To take Boydell & Brewer as a case study of this: as an independent publisher, they were unable to work with Project MUSE, whose own governance requires that presses they work with be non-profits. While Boydell & Brewer is an [employee-owned co-operative](#) and highly mission-driven, they are also set up as a commercial entity. Therefore, they instead chose to work with Fulcrum to host and manage their backlist packages for a set annual fee, and opted, as with our other publishers, to make their OtF offer

available via Lyrasis (and hopefully Jisc) to most easily access global library subscribers. The flexibility and intangibility of OtF made it extremely easy for us to involve Fulcrum as a new third party.

Another example is Basler Afrika Bibliographien (BAB). They already had a close and long-standing relationship with the African Books Collective, an infrastructure to support African scholarship on and from the region. While they were eligible to work with Project MUSE, BAB decided, after discussions with us and the African Books Collective, that they wanted to administer access to the backlist packages with the ABC, and to engage in a revenue split with ABC rather than pay one-off annual fees. Once again, the great flexibility of the model enabled this to happen with ease and speed, contemporaneously with both B&B's arrangement with Fulcrum, LUP's ongoing use of Atypion, and CEUP and MSUP's use of Project MUSE. We could easily envisage, for example, a regional split in infrastructure; for example, other publisher members of the ABC could theoretically adopt the model with the same arrangement with them as BAB has, while North American publishers could instead opt for Fulcrum. The fact that so many of the logistics, processes and adaptable templates are documented on the Copim Compass should support this process.

Conclusions and Final Points

As noted at the start of this piece, Opening the Future, like the rest of the Copim Open Book Futures project, was a practice research project. It implemented an experimental collective funding model for books that was aimed at small, mission-driven traditional presses who were trying to find a sustainable but equitable way into OA publishing. It investigated if such a model would work in the real world beyond the Copim phase 1 pilot, and if publishers and libraries would be willing to engage with it.

Our project reached all of its project targets around investigating this, and has demonstrated a willingness from libraries to fund this approach to OA books, despite the enormous pressures library budgets have seen in the UK, US and elsewhere since the project began. We also met the set parameters for demonstrating a similar willingness from publishers, as demonstrated by our deliverable to onboard three new publishers and the many conversations we had with other presses. However, as noted, we also discovered that many of the publishers we had discussions with (around 80%) were unable to participate due to, primarily, a lack of spare time necessary to implement the model, uncertainty on whether implementing OA funding was the best use of the limited human and financial resources available to them, and a lack of confidence in their ability to continue to implement the model after April 2026 when project support would end.

The somewhat informal, unstructured nature of OtF was foundational to it, and was by design. This was both a blessing and a curse, as we began to note in [our first blog post on planning for post-project](#), published back in April 2024. In many ways this has been highly effective, enabling us to be very agile and to move quickly in responding to both issues and opportunities, a quality necessary in this ever-evolving field. Our personal relationships with our publishers have been foundational to our success, and indeed our pilot publishers were heavily involved in the initial design. Our strong relationships of trust with third parties were also instrumental in mapping out our future. But our reliance on, and assumptions around, the strength and sustainability of these more unstructured

connections has also proven to be very difficult, and fundamentally, we both wholly agree that an overarching infrastructure of some kind is necessary for collective funding to be successful, particularly at the small scale our publishers operate on. While direct relationships between libraries and publishers were a key factor in early collective funding initiatives such as OBP, OLH and punctum, as the field grows, this becomes less viable, as participation via billing agents becomes the standard expectation from libraries, and as publishers who do engage in collective funding models must find ways to stand out from the increasingly large numbers of competitors, all vying for still relatively modest library funds.

With hindsight, perhaps more time and resources could have been invested into a landscape review during the design phase, which may have canvassed more publishers about the feasibility of working in the way that Opening the Future originally envisioned, and which could have gathered a wider set of library perspectives on what changes, and what rate of change, seemed likely to them around their acquisitions and OA budget structures. This review might have prioritised the creation from the start of a long-term 'home', whether that meant establishing Opening the Future as its own infrastructure, or entering into discussions with third parties at an earlier stage and with more concrete plans. However, it is also undeniable that there have been many upsides to the approach that we took instead, chief among these that it has seeded a wide variety of new possibilities; many different publisher types (both non-profit and for-profit) have options of different infrastructures they can partner with, on different terms, to achieve their OA frontlist publishing goals.

We look forward to seeing how these iterations at, Fulcrum, Project MUSE, the African Books Collective, and perhaps elsewhere will develop and what new cross-contaminations can occur in the shared Community of Practice that will provide the necessary commonality and third space for our publishers to meet with each other and interested librarians. It remains our earnest hope that people will take the documentation we've made available online and use these tools, and some of the warnings and suggestions from this document, to build something new, and to participate in the future iterations of Opening the Future where they align with the Community of Practice. We also note that our work has been influential on initiatives entirely unaligned with our Work Package or Copim, including UPLOpen, the De Gruyter collective funding model for university presses, which [cited Opening the Future](#) as a forerunner from whom they gained insights. Although we have not been directly cited by other models, we have noted strong similarities between Opening the Future and Taylor and Francis' [Pledge to Open](#) scheme which came some years after us. Bloomsbury Academic's collective funding model ([Bloomsbury Open Collections](#)) which was also launched several years after OtF has many resemblances to our first-of-its-kind model in the monograph sphere. Opening the Future has scattered seeds of its model widely, and we look forward to seeing what takes firm root and what doesn't, and how differently these all grow.

The [Ithaka S+R report cited earlier](#), emphasised that OtF and other models like it:

...strengthen the capacity of university presses and independent publishers to produce open access monographs—whether immediately or through phased approaches—are viewed as essential in protecting these presses' capacities to publish alternative voices. As such, these open monograph efforts underpin the

sustainability of these publishers and also safeguard their ability to curate and disseminate specialized and underrepresented areas of scholarship to a wide range of readers.

We also discovered in the course of the project that it was not realistic for small or medium-sized publishers to entirely 'go it alone' on implementing a collective funding model, and that a third party infrastructure of some kind was necessary for sustainability. This would be important for its ongoing implementation with the current publishers, and, we realised, would be necessary to encourage new publishers to participate as well. While we believe that, as the field becomes more entrenched, staff at smaller publishers may develop the skills and find the time to implement their own collective funding schemes, other developments (like those at Jisc) and their impact on our ability to reach UK libraries suggest that large-scale and shared infrastructure may remain an important factor into the future. While we have not discussed the logistics of library outreach much here, this also reflects the development of some of our outreach strategies over time, as we found that scale was a factor here too. Towards the end of the project, we began to focus our time and effort onto consortial outreach as consortia allowed us to access multiple libraries as potential members through one point of contact. In some ways, this perhaps reflects the broader phase of 'scaling up' that the landscape seems to be going through, as large collective funding group initiatives such as the Open Book Collective, JSTOR's Path to Open and UPLOpen proliferate, and as MIT Press, who launched their individual collective funding model in 2021 also began acting for Duke University Press and Goldsmith's College in 2025/6. The focus on scale, when taken in conjunction with the increasing necessity to involve third party billing partners and the proliferation of evaluation criteria from library and consortia who seek to categorise and sift through different collective funding offerings, perhaps point to an increasing professionalisation of collective funding for books, the impact of which remains to be seen.

There is another consideration to note here, related to the nature of our outreach strategy and that is to acknowledge that what WP3 has engaged in has been only that: outreach and advocacy, not sales. We have no sales background but that has perhaps been a benefit to us: perhaps our moderate success can be attributed to a more library-centred approach, where networking, trust, and transparency are valued and are compelling in persuading budget-holders to invest in a new paradigm for supporting book publishing. If we think of OtF first and foremost as an OA funding programme with a backlist sweetener (as the Copim WP3 team does) then this statement probably stands. But if a press thinks of it as a backlist collection sale with an OA sweetener then a traditional sales team would be useful of course. The larger publishers, and particularly the commercial ones, running collective models of various stripes have the benefit of sales teams and existing sales networks - it remains to be seen if these are necessary to ensure the survival of the proliferating models as they evolve from the successful and longstanding frontlist OA model pioneers like Open Book Publishers, punctum books, and OAPEN and OLH.

Opening the Future was never designed to be a permanent model. Theoretically, this would be impossible, because increased success undermines a core facet of the model: the more successful Opening the Future is, the more of the publisher's frontlist is open access. Therefore, the less closed backlist accrues to create future packages, and eventually the model collapses. This too was by design, and this is an aspect we fundamentally stand by. The backlist packages have allowed many libraries to

participate in Opening the Future who may not have been able to participate in a ‘pure’ OA frontlist support model, but this was designed to be a bridging exercise towards OA support. Professor Martin Eve, the model’s architect, described this concept as “[come for the backlist and stay for the OA](#)”. On an individual basis we have seen this happen a small number of times, where a library signs up at first for a backlist package, and then renews after three years via an OA membership (that is a library membership option we offer at Opening the Future without backlist content attached to it, i.e. pure frontlist support).

But more broadly we still see Opening the Future as a stepping stone as library budgets overall become more amenable to supporting collective funding. This brings us back to one of the early points of this piece: that we were wrong about the rate of change that was possible within library budget structures, and were also wrong about how quickly this would become a major priority for publishers. We may also have overestimated how quickly the value of the backlist packages would wear off. As noted earlier, these packages remain a major draw for libraries. Despite now publishing about half their annual monograph frontlist OA, CEU Press were still able to set up [a new backlist package in 2024](#) and another ‘midlist’ package in 2025 [using only titles from the last five years](#). And as the formation of the current packages shows, even a relatively deep backlist to the earlier 2000s has value. While we remain confident that OA generally, and collective funding in particular, remains a major direction of travel, and that using backlist remains a good lever to open the right doors within libraries, the timescale over which this is all happening, and will continue to happen, is longer than we originally hoped.

Undeniably, we have participated in the successful growth of the collective funding field for books and, as our first publishers now move into their fifth year of fruitful participation, we also believe that our work has helped to demonstrate the mid-term sustainability of these models. We have done this in two ways: via the direct successes of our publishers, and via the influence our model has had in subsequent model design. We also see many reasons for optimism about the future of Opening the Future as it begins to diversify and branch. No subsequent model has had quite the same focus as OtF: that of helping smaller and ‘traditional’ presses to transition to open access sustainably and with as little risk as possible. However, the urgent need to facilitate this kind of transition remains as pressing as ever, in particular with the implementation of the REF requirement for OA books still due to come into effect in the near future. Much reporting has been done by Copim (but also by independent consultants like [Knowledge Exchange](#) and [Information Power](#)) on the barriers to smaller and society publishers participating in OA, which often focuses on the difficulties of making OA books work financially, and of transitioning to OA, for these smaller publishers. We strongly believe that, one way or another, the model hypothesised, tested, and refined by Work Package 3 and Opening the Future has a part to play in this ongoing and needed transition.

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